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GINGER: A SHOPPING CART INTERACTIVE PROGRAM

A CASE STUDY FOR RELATIONAL-CULTURAL THEORY AND ACTIVITY THEORY IN INTERACTION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Empathy, authenticity and mutuality are three central tenets in relational-cultural theory. Although developed as a therapeutic process, when combined with activity theory, interaction designers can create relationship with users of their designed products. Technology often interferes with the growth of a relationship. Ginger, a shopping cart interactive program, is an application that demonstrates a growth fostering relationship between designer and user. Ginger guides the user through the grocery retail environment. The Ginger application was designed to improve shoppers' connection with the grocery retail environment. Nutrition is central to human life. Eating the right foods can significantly impact one's quality of life. With the capabilities of the Ginger application to provide an interface that can display readable nutrition information on a wireless device and tailor to the specific dietary restrictions of its users, it will enable shoppers to have a less frustrating experience while shopping for food.

Keywords: Interaction design, relational-cultural theory, activity theory.

INTRODUCTION

Creative design and science have historically been enemies. While design is often based on subjectivity, science is based on neutral objectivity. Interaction design begins with the needs and desires from the people that will use a product, and depends on both subjective and qualitative values (Moggridge, 2007). Ginger was designed initially on the basis of subjectivity and used quantitative usability testing to form an iterative design process as a scientific

research method. Relational-cultural theory was used as a basis to determine the users' emotional connection to the application, while activity theory was used to define the activity of a user within the grocery retail environment. The following paper begins by describing the current situation of users within the grocery retail environment, then examines how relational-cultural theory and activity theory can be combined in interaction design, concluding with possible solutions and future directions for further research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Using relational-cultural theory in combination with activity theory will demonstrate how this combination could apply to the design process. A case study is presented and an example of design development is introduced. The case study began with the design of two low-fidelity prototypes in which user testing was conducted and is presented in this research. The data collected is from five users. An example will be presented to show how this combination was used in the design process.

EXISTING CONDITIONS

Our population is significantly aging. The first of the Baby Boomer generation (those born between 1946 and 1964) will turn 65 in 2011. It is estimated that 20% of the population will be 65 or older by 2030 (Czaja & Lee, 2001). Physiological changes associated with aging, such as decrements of sight, hearing, dexterity, motor functioning, hand-eye coordination and cognitive processing, make new screen technologies more difficult to use (Selwyn, *et al* 2003). These changes occur regardless of gender, race or culture, and can have significant impact on quality of life. What used

to be a simple trip to the grocery store may not be so simple for those experiencing these changes of aging.

The ability to read food and product information at the grocery store in a clear, concise and consistent format, is important to sustaining independence. Adults with dietary restrictions, such as the need for lower sodium intake, diabetes, and/or allergies, make it imperative to be able to read all nutritional information on packaging. This includes the nutrition facts, drug facts, supplement facts, as well as the complete list of ingredients. There is a lack of consistency in product packaging and not all information is visually presented in the same manner. This lack of consistency can create frustration in shoppers, in addition to the text sizes being too small for aging eyes to read, it can cause illness for someone with a dietary restriction that cannot properly read a product's contents.

The purpose of this project is to discover the proper design strategies for an application to be developed for a wireless device (i.e. Apple's iPad) to be used in a grocery retail environment. The device will function with Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) tags placed on each product in the grocery store. The device will receive the product information and present it in a clear, concise and consistent format so shoppers will be able to read all of the nutrition facts and ingredients listed on a package.

During the evaluation phase of this project, the following questions were answered with Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved usability testing, 1) Are adults age 46 and over receptive to using the Web-based application, and 2) Will the application prove easy to navigate.

DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

According to Lee Rainie at Pew Internet & American Life Project, between the years 2000 and 2010, the number of older adults (aged 46 and over) using the Internet increased from 40% to 74%. Using the same comparisons, 63% have broadband at home, 81% own a cell phone, 46% connect to the Internet wirelessly and greater than 50% use cloud computing (Rainie, 2010).

This group comprises those in the Baby Boomer generation (born 1946-1964), the Silent Generation (born 1930-1945), WWII children (born 1915-1930),

and children of the Great Depression (born prior to 1915). While this group has enormity in numbers, it is not homogenous. Although similarities do exist, American society recognizes the life course theory through labeling blocks of years for any given population segment such as: young adult, adult, middle-aged adults, older adults, retired adults and very old adults (Steenblock, 2010). While difficult, accepting these labels requires acknowledgment and realization of our advancing age in physical, psychological and social areas (Coburn & Lawrence-Treeger, 1997).

COMBINING METHODOLOGIES

Activity theory was used as a model to measure the social and cultural relationships (Kang & Satterfield, 2009) of the participants within the grocery retail environment.

The activity theory model contains three mutual relationships between subject, object and community (Kuuti, 1996). In this paper the subject is the person, the object is the grocery store and the community is those within a family unit that shop for food either alone or together, as well as the community of people within the grocery store. This includes the employees and other shoppers.

The introduction of the Ginger application is another mutual relationship between subject and object, in the already existing object of the grocery store. By introducing Ginger into an already existing environment, a change in relationship occurs. Ginger becomes a mediating tool between the object of the grocery store, the community and the subject (Kuuti, 1996).

Using empathy, authenticity and mutuality, the tenets of relational-cultural theory, the designs were developed to create relationship between designer and user and ultimately between user and grocery store. Western psychology contains many theories stemming from a position of cultural dominance (Walker, 2004) and the predisposition to appear scientifically objective or neutral. It is important not only to consider the user within the context of the grocery store, but also consider the user's cultural experience as a whole.

The first tenet of relational-cultural theory is empathy. Respect is the foundation of empathy, which is a complex cognitive-affective skill that

involves the ability to join with another in his or her experience (Jordan, 2002). Rather than a designer taking the stance of “power-over” the user, the designer can be in “power-with” the user by offering an empathic design solution (Miller, 1976). In “power-over” relationships the dominant culture works in ways that maintain the power differential. In “power-with” relationships, there is shared energy that facilitates productive movement (Walker, 2004). A predominant number of IT professionals in the United States are male. “The Information Technology Association of America (ITAA) finds that women and most racial minorities remain significantly underrepresented in today’s U.S. information technology (IT) workforce” (ITAA, 2005). This brings questions of privilege and power to the fold since men outnumber women three to one in the IT industry, which includes interaction design. Feminist author bell hooks writes, “By listening to the voices at the margins of patriarchal culture, the model can envision new alternatives for the center” (Walker, 2004). Using the concept of mutuality to create mutually empowering connections, designers of differing gender, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, class concerns, or health status, can eliminate exclusionary bias in designing for under represented groups. Mutuality is a creative process in which contributions of each person and openness to change allow something new to happen (Walker, 2004). The design process for this research began with the question, “How can relationship increase capacity for resilience and empower movement toward connection in the Ginger application?” (Walker, 2004). The final tenet of relational-cultural theory is authenticity. Miller (1976) describes “authenticity as an increasing capacity for representing oneself more fully in relationship.” Ginger’s purpose is to contribute to bettering the human existence, not to make exorbitant profits. Ken Garland’s *First Things First Manifesto* (1964) makes salient points that the essence of design is not about commercialism. Authenticity in this sense is about contributing to the greater good, regardless of financial gain.

DESIGN CONCEPT

The older adult age group consists of varying socioeconomic levels and varying degrees of

technological savvy. The participants represented a variety of age, gender, and cultural groups (Kang & Satterfield, 2009). The concept was to develop an application for the grocery retail environment to address the issues of physiological changes that occur with aging when shopping at the grocery store. Accessing product information about food, supplements and drugs in a clear, concise and consistent format, was the main focus for developing the Ginger application.

Part of the concept is for the grocery store to provide a wireless device (i.e. Apple’s iPad) that can be mounted on a shopping cart with a closed, secure WiFi network. Differing socioeconomic groups of older adults would have access to the benefits of this device by the store providing it. A user could also use her own wireless device to login securely to the store’s network. All shoppers of the grocery store of any age would be able to use the device, in addition to the older adult demographic that was researched for this project.

Each product in the store would be labeled with a RFID tag that the wireless device would read via a wireless antenna contained in the tag over the store’s secure, closed WiFi network. RFID tags would complement barcodes and barcode readers, since they are more efficient, easier for devices to read and are capable of storing large amounts of information in their microchip. Nutritional information, pricing, expiration date, country of origin, size, weight, and further product information can be stored in the RFID tag related to a specific user’s shopping needs.

Thomas Friedman, in his book (2007) *The World is Flat*, refers to RFID technology by stating, “This is clearly the wave of the future. RFID technology and sophisticated order analysis tools that monitor even the most minute market activity are rapidly leading us toward industry’s holy grail—absolute balance in supply and demand.” (Friedman, 2007).

The mounting bracket on the cart would be adjustable to accommodate differing user heights and reduce glare, as well as allowing users with their own mobile devices to be able to mount them on the cart.

Two different low-fidelity prototypes of user interfaces were designed, User Interface 1 (UI1) and User Interface 2 (UI2), for the Ginger application

(Wiley, *et al* 2010). Both interfaces followed the same navigational flow and displayed the same types of information.

The following graphic design guidelines were taken into account when the interfaces were designed (National Institute on Aging, 2004):

- **Typeface:** Use a sans serif typeface that is not condensed. Avoid the use of serif, novelty, and display typefaces.
- **Type size:** Use 12 point or 14 point type size for body text.
- **Type weight:** Use medium or bold face type.
- **Capital and lowercase letters:** Present body text in upper and lowercase letters. Use all capital letters and italics in headlines only. Reserve underlining for links.
- **Physical spacing:** Double space all body text
- **Justification:** There are three ways to justify type; left, full, or centered justified. Left justified text is optimal for older adults.
- **Color:** Avoid yellow and blue and green in close proximity. These colors and juxtapositions are difficult for some older adults to discriminate. Ensure that text and graphics are understandable when viewed on a black and white monitor.
- **Backgrounds:** Use dark type or graphics against a light background, or white lettering on a black or dark-colored background. Avoid patterned backgrounds.

In regards to navigation through different screens, the team lessened the amount of vertical scrolling, kept the layout consistent, eliminated the need for a mouse by using a touch screen interface with a virtual keyboard, incorporated text with icons, used pull-down menus sparingly, and incorporated backward and forward navigation arrows on each page.

USER TESTING

Both of the UI designs depend on the user already being registered in the Ginger program. The registration process can be completed at a store with the assistance of customer service or online via secure Web site. The user would fill out a submit form with their dietary restrictions so the Ginger

application would be able to warn the user if any product in their shopping cart contains the ingredient(s) that is among their restrictions. For instance, if a user is allergic to peanuts, then the Ginger application would display a warning if that ingredient was present in the product when it was placed in the cart.

The user would also be able to compare the nutrition facts with another product. For example, the sodium content per serving in two different kinds of canned soup could be compared to see which contains the lowest amount. This feature would be useful for someone keeping track of sodium intake.

In order to remove an item from the cart, the user simply places it back on the shelf as the device automatically removes it from the cart's contents. Once the user is ready to checkout, the checkout button is touched and the registered user's banking information or credit/debit card on file is charged for their purchases. This eliminates waiting in a checkout line to have the cashier scan each item and receive payment. The user can choose to bag their own groceries while shopping, or have a store employee bag their groceries upon checkout.

PROTOTYPES

Two different low-fidelity prototypes of user interfaces were designed and tested (Figures 1 & 2) for the Ginger application. Both interfaces followed the same navigational flow and displayed the same types of information. However, the visual presentation of elements varied drastically. Prototype UI1 was based on using icons with text and prototype UI2 was a predominantly text-based navigation set within a modular grid format.

Figure 1. UI1 prototype screens.

Figure 2. UI2 prototype screens.

TESTING PROCESS

The two prototypes were tested during the same usability testing sessions with five users that were selected from a pool of respondents within the target demographic of adults age 46 and over. User demographics are displayed in Table 1.

User Demographic Facts Summary	
Question	%Breakdown
Age range	80% 46-55
Gender	60% female/40% male
Native language	(5 users total) 60% English
Occupation	80% Professional
Computer use	100% Daily
Web use	100% Daily
Cell phone use	80% Daily
Use a smart phone	60%
Used iPad before	60%
Shop online	60%
Grocery shop routine	80% Weekly
Neither of the males in the study had dietary restrictions, but all three women had at least one. Two out of three women needed reduced sodium and reduced sugar intake. 60% of the users have problems reading the nutritional facts on food product packaging and 40% have problems reading the ingredients.	

Table 1. User demographics.

CONCLUSIONS

UI2 was redesigned as part of the iterative design process since 80% of the users preferred it. An interesting correlation became apparent in terms of color preference and gender. The color preference for UI2, was 60% (all of the female users) found the color palette of orange and grey pleasing. The male users (40% or all of the male users) strongly disagreed with the color choices.

The color palette of blue and grey used in UI1, created a mixture of pleasing versus not pleasing. Only one female user and one male user found the colors attractive.

The warm colors of orange and grey were used in the redesign of UI2, but the visual representation of data was restructured greatly in accordance with user feedback.

Further design and usability testing will be conducted with focus on building an emotional connection to the user based on the relational-cultural theory's tenets of empathy, mutuality and authenticity.

The emotional connection would encourage user participation with the application and create a more pleasurable shopping experience overall. The more bold color palette will be used to create contrast and evoke an emotional response from the user. Ginger will be given an avatar of the same name that will guide the user through the grocery retail environment.

Figure 2. Redesigned UI2.

In addition to adding a more emotional connection, haptic feedback will be added to the interface. Using sounds and vibration will help the user feel that the interface is responding to their actions. Activity theory was used in this research to show how the Ginger application would fit into users' actual

social and material environments in the grocery store (Nardi, 1996). Relational-cultural theory was used as a foundation to designing interactions for an under represented group with empathy, mutuality and authenticity.

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